

APC-driven actin nucleation powers collective cell dynamics in colorectal cancer cells

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ABSTRACT

Cell remodeling relies on dynamic rearrangements of cell contacts powered by the actin cytoskeleton. The tumor suppressor Adenomatous Polyposis Coli (APC) nucleates actin filaments (F-actin) and localizes at cell junctions. Whether APC-driven actin nucleation acts in cell junction remodeling remains unknown. To explore that possibility, we have combined bioimaging and genetic tools with artificial intelligence algorithms applied to colorectal cancer cell monolayers. We found that the APC-dependent actin pool contributes to sustaining levels of F-actin and adhesive components at cell junctions. Moreover, this activity preserved cell junction length, angle and motion, as well as vertex motion and integrity. Finally, the loss of this F-actin pool led to larger cells with slow and random cell movement within a sheet. Our findings suggest that APC-driven actin nucleation promotes cell junction integrity and dynamics to facilitate collective cell remodeling and consequent motility. Our study offers a new perspective to explore the relevance of APC-driven cytoskeletal function in gut morphogenesis.

INTRODUCTION

In the gut, cell-cell junction remodeling is key to safeguard the integrity of the epithelial barrier and to provide structural support for the epithelial monolayers¹⁻⁸. In this context, the actin cytoskeleton controls the abundance of adhesive molecules at cell-cell junctions, restricts the mobility of the cell adhesion components at the membrane and supports the integrity of cell junctions⁸⁻¹¹. Moreover, a mesh of actin is assembled under the cytoplasmic membrane which is critical for contractility of cells and their resulting architecture^{12,13}. Furthermore, actin-rich protrusions generate force for cells to migrate out of the crypts towards the villi tips where they are shed off^{14,15}.

The tumor suppressor Adenomatous Polyposis Coli (APC) is considered the master regulator of gut homeostasis¹⁶⁻¹⁸. Mutations in APC, most of them sporadic, have been found in >80% of colorectal cancer cases^{16,19}, and many lead to alterations in gut organization including the presence of (precancerous) polyps. Loss of heterozygosity via somatic mutation drives tumorigenesis. For instance, patients with inherited syndrome familial adenomatous polyposis (FAP) present hundreds of polyps formed in early adulthood with very high risk to progress to cancer by the age of forty^{20,21}.

Much of our current knowledge on the roles of APC has been inferred from studies using gene silencing, knock-outs, or expression of truncated proteins lacking the C-terminal part of APC. Yet, APC is a multi-functional 2843-amino acid protein with multiple interacting partners. As such, the full biological significance of APC's broad range of activities is far from clear. Historically, APC's cytoskeletal roles have been overlooked [19], although they might play significant functions in organizing the gut epithelium, independent of APC's control of cell proliferation via Wnt signaling²². We have previously generated a specific 'separation-of-function' APC mutant - herein named APC-m4²³. APC-m4 is abrogated in F-actin nucleation but capable of binding actin monomers²³. Transient transfection of APC-m4 in U2OS osteosarcoma and MDA-MB231 breast cancer cells caused a delay in focal adhesion turnover and migration of single cells²³⁻²⁵.

Evidence showed that full-length APC is required for proper localization of tight and adherens components at cell junctions, an association dependent on an 'active' actin cytoskeleton²⁶⁻²⁹. SW480 colorectal cancer cell line expresses a truncated version of APC that lacks the C-terminal domain, where the cytoskeleton activity resides. Reintroduction of full-length APC protein in SW480 rescues the localization of adhesive components and F-actin at adherens junctions, strengthening cell adhesion with concomitant changes in cell morphology and motility as assessed by a wound assay^{26,30}.

These precedents raise the question of whether APC-driven actin nucleation activity may contribute to any collective cell remodeling event at cell junctions and consequent motility-associated event(s) critical for gut homeostasis. Here we have implemented a combination of genetics, cell imaging tools and artificial intelligence algorithms applied to the study of colorectal cancer cell monolayers to investigate the impact of APC-driven actin nucleation on a) the levels and dynamics of cell adhesion components, b) cell size, c) the directionality of cell migration within a sheet. Our data establish a role for APC in coordinating actin with cell adhesion dynamics to control collective cell remodeling and directed cell motility in colorectal cancer.

RESULTS

Actin nucleation mediated by APC is required for maintaining proper levels and dynamics of adhesive proteins at cell junctions

We have explored whether APC-driven actin nucleation activity may contribute to any collective cell remodeling event at cell junctions, which could be critical in the gut epithelium. To that end, we have generated colorectal (adeno)carcinoma-derived epithelial cellular lines (SW480 and HCT116) expressing stably wild type APC (APC-WT) or the mutant APC-m4 (Fig S1 A-D; see Methods). These newly generated stable cell lines were used to assess F-actin at cell-cell junctions in cells grown as monolayers. We first grew SW480 expressing stably APC-WT and APC-m4 epithelial monolayers, fixed and stained cells with Alexa-488-phalloidin. Confocal laser scanning microscopy showed that in SW480 APC-WT cells F-Actin localized at cell junctions, as expected (Figure 1A-B). In contrast, in APC-m4 cells, F-Actin was more diffused at cell junctions and presented an enhanced cytoplasmic signal (Figure 1B). In addition, the label at APC-WT cell junctions appeared smooth and continuous compared to puncta marking cell junctions in APC-m4 cells. Based on the appearance of F-actin label at cell junctions, we divided cells into three groups: '*normal*', '*discontinuous*', and '*round*'. From this qualitative analysis, we found that 67.49% of APC-WT cells displayed '*normal*' F-actin at the junctions compared to 18.24% of APC-m4 cells, 26.16% of APC-WT cells presented '*discontinuous label*' compared to 59.20% of APC-m4 cells, and no significant differences were found for the '*round*' category between APC-WT and APC-m4 cells (Figure 1A). A similar distribution of F-actin label, and therefore distribution of '*normal*', '*discontinuous*', and '*round*' cells, was observed in HCT116 APC-WT and APC-m4 monolayers (Figure S1E). Together, these findings suggest that loss of APC-driven actin nucleation significantly compromised F-actin localization at cell junctions in monolayers.

Subsequently, we asked whether the F-actin pool generated by APC had any effect on the levels of F-actin at cell junctions, and/or levels and dynamics of adhesive components at cell junctions. To answer those questions, we stained SW480 APC-WT or APC-m4 monolayers with antibodies to visualize phalloidin (F-actin marker) along with Occludin (a classic tight junction marker) by immunofluorescence. Dual-color imaging showed that F-Actin and Occludin localized at cell junctions in APC-WT cells as expected (Figure 1B). However, both labels were spread into the cytoplasm in APC-m4 cells (Figure 1B). Quantitative analysis showed a significant decrease in the fluorescence intensity of F-actin and Occludin; Specifically, at the cell-cell junctions of APC-m4 cells compared to the same labels in APC-WT cells (Figure 1C-D). Our results support a role for F-actin nucleation by APC in stabilizing a pool of actin and junctional proteins at cell junctions.

To examine whether the loss of actin generated by APC had any effect on cell junction dynamics, we transiently transfected SW480 APC-WT and APC-m4 with E-cadherin protein fused to a GFP-tag – a classic marker for adherens junctions. Using live imaging in a confocal laser scanner microscope, we analyzed various junctional parameters in monolayers (Figure 1E-K, Video 1). APC-WT cells had straighter junctions which stayed almost unchanged in length over the 20-minute observation window (Figure 1G-F). In contrast, a significant variation in both junction length and angle were observed in APC-m4 cells (Figure 1G-F). Additionally, we quantified the movement of each cell junction over time by drawing a perpendicular line to each junction using this region of interest to acquire kymographs. Junction velocity was determined from the kymograph slope. We found that APC-m4 junctions had a higher velocity than APC-WT ($\sim 3.7 \times 10^{-3}$ vs $\sim 4.3 \times 10^{-3}$ $\mu\text{m}/\text{sec}$, Figure 1H). Together these data indicated that the loss of F-actin nucleation by APC led to greater plasticity of cell junctions.

From our timelapses, we noticed that cell junctions, but especially the tricellular adhesive sites (herein named vertexes) at cell junctions exhibited less E-cadherin in APC-m4 cells relative to APC-WT cells (Figure 1E). Given that recent evidence showed that changes in E-cadherin levels at the vertexes of cell junctions affect their motion and generate asymmetry of vertex contraction³¹, we investigated various vertex parameters in APC-m4. We observed that vertexes were more disrupted in the mutant cells over time. Analysis of vertex integrity revealed that $\sim 26\%$ of APC-m4 junctions had intact junction vertexes in contrast to $\sim 85\%$ of APC-WT (Figure 1K). Moreover, instances of single or both vertexes being disrupted were $\sim 34\%$ and $\sim 40\%$, respectively, in APC-m4, compared to only $\sim 10\%$ and $\sim 5\%$, respectively, in APC-WT (Figure 1K). In addition, vertex velocities in APC-m4 junctions were higher compared to APC-WT junctions ($\sim 4 \times 10^{-3}$ vs $\sim 4.5 \times 10^{-3}$ $\mu\text{m}/\text{sec}$; Figure 1I). Furthermore, both APC-WT vertexes in a junction had similar velocities (Figure 1J). However, APC-m4 vertexes in a junction moved at significantly different velocities ($\sim 6 \times 10^{-4}$ $\mu\text{m}/\text{sec}$ difference; Figure 1J). Together, these data demonstrate that cells expressing APC-m4 presented lower levels of adhesive components, developed less stable and robust junctions with vertexes displaying different strength and motility compared to the junctions and corresponding vertexes of cells expressing APC-WT as control.

Given that our findings showed a prominent defect in the integrity and dynamics of cell junctions by light microscopy, we sought to further investigate whether APC-mediated actin nucleation affected the ultrastructure of cell junctions using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). We found that APC-WT monolayers presented well-formed and interdigitated junctions (Figure 1L). Recent studies have argued that the formation of membrane protrusions engaging in the form of a 'handshake' or 'tethering nanotubes' (known as TENT) is critical to maintaining cohesive junctions^{7,32}. Accordingly, we clearly observed TENT structures in APC-WT cell junctions (Figure 1L). In sharp contrast, no interdigitation between cell junctions and barely any TENTs were observed in the APC-m4 SEM images (Figure 1L). These results confirmed that the

structural connections between cells were strongly perturbed in the mutant (Figure 1L). These data suggest that APC-driven actin nucleation is key to preserving robust integrity and dynamics of the components at cell junctions, as well as facilitating tight structural bonds between cells.

Loss of APC-driven actin nucleation results in larger cells

The actin cytoskeleton is central to cell shape^{3,33–36}. From our images, it seemed that some APC-m4 cells – impaired in actin nucleation – were larger than APC-WT cells. We therefore analyzed the size of individual APC-WT and APC-m4 cells grown as an adherent monolayer. We used a customized version of a deep-learning-based segmentation method called Cellpose³⁷. Quantification of HCT116 APC-WT and APC-m4 cells showed differences in size (187.6 μm^2 and 203.8 μm^2 , respectively; Figure 2A-B). To further validate our results, we also measured the cell size in the SW480 colorectal cancer cell line in which the endogenous APC lacks the C-terminal region (where the actin-related function resides). A similar trend was found between SW480 APC-WT and APC-m4, though more pronounced than in the HCT116 APC-WT and APC-m4 cells (Figure 2C-D versus Figure 2A-B). Together, these data demonstrated that the change in cell size could be attributed to the lack of actin nucleation activity by APC.

APC also synergizes with additional nucleation proteins including formin^{38–40} to further promote actin filament polymerization *in vitro*^{23,41–43}. To determine whether formin-dependent actin polymerization contributes to cell size changes, we grew SW480 APC-WT and APC-m4 monolayers and treated them with the pan-formin small-molecule inhibitor SMIFH2 for 1 hour^{44,45}. All cell monolayers were fixed, and individual cell sizes calculated. Double inhibition of formin and APC-dependent actin activity did not result in any significant difference in cell-spread area compared to single inhibition in the mutant (Figure 2E).

To rule out that the defects observed in APC-m4 cell size were caused by changes in cell division, we performed flow cytometry analysis to determine the percentage of SW480 APC-WT or APC-m4 cells at different stages of the cell cycle (G1, M and G2). No significant differences were found at any cell stage (Figure 2F-G). Overall, these results support that cell size maintenance requires proper functioning of APC-driven actin nucleation - independent of formin function and cell proliferation.

APC-mediated actin nucleation governs collective cell migration

Collective cell migration requires a constant modification of cell shape, which is intrinsically coupled with dynamic remodeling of the actin cytoskeleton^{46–48}. Therefore, we explored whether collective cell migration was compromised in APC-m4 colorectal

cancer cells. To address this, HCT116 cells expressing APC-WT or APC-m4 were grown as monolayers, scratched to create a wound and imaged during healing (Figure 3A, Video 2). We analyzed the trajectories of individual cells migrating at wounds over time and quantified directionality, migration speed, accumulated traveled and Euclidean distances (the shortest distance between two points, see Methods). We observed that the APC-m4 cell trajectories were more erratic, (cells moved significantly slower and covered shorter distances than the APC-WT cells) indicating random cell migration (Figure 3 B-F). In addition, we observed that mutant cells exhibited a high incidence of cell detachment (Figure 3A, Video 2), also contributing to the loss of coherent directionality. Similar results were observed in SW480 colorectal cell monolayers (Figure S2). These results implicate APC-driven actin nucleation in promoting proper directionality and speed of colorectal cells moving as a collection.

DISCUSSION

In this study, we have exploited the power of a specific 'separation-of-function' APC mutant named APC-m4 that specifically abrogates actin nucleation function²³ to probe APC's involvement in cell-cell junction integrity via the actin cytoskeleton. Our study offers crucial mechanistic insight to bridge the gap between two functional links previously proposed: APC and cell junctions, and F-actin and cell junctions. Specifically, our findings integrate these two links by highlighting the requirement of APC-driven actin nucleation activity to sustain cell junction integrity and strength, cell size, and consequent directionality of cell migration.

It has been shown that cells expressing truncated APC proteins lacking the C-terminus exhibit reduced levels of cadherin molecules at cell junctions^{30,49}. In turn, the expression of full-length APC restores cadherin protein levels, suggesting a relevant role of the C-terminal domain of APC³⁰. Others proposed that a mesh of F-actin surrounds cadherin clusters to act as an 'insulator' or 'corral' to delimit their location, fusion and mobility^{11,50}. Indeed, inhibition of formin activity reduces both F-actin and E-cadherin levels, with concomitant perturbation of cadherin stability at cell junctions⁵¹. It is believed that rearrangements at cell junctions may be governed by forces yet to be defined in mechanistic terms. For example, actomyosin-based contractility might induce conformational changes in adhesive proteins, in turn, affecting their stability and/or binding to partners⁵²⁻⁵⁵. Interestingly, modulation of E-cadherin levels at the vertexes of cell junctions affects their motion and generates asymmetry of vertex (and therefore cell junction) contraction³¹.

Dynamic cell shape, subject to remodeling of the actin cytoskeleton, is critical to proper cell migration^{3,33,47,56}. Interestingly, active cell migration along the villus-axis in the gut is supported by actin-rich protrusions nucleated by the actin-related protein 2/3 (Arp2/3) complex. Those generate the force for cells to move up to the villus tip where they will be shed⁵⁷. A recent study implicated APC localized at microtubule tips in the stimulation of Arp2/3-dependent nucleation of branched actin protrusions⁵⁸.

Here we show that expression of APC-m4 in colorectal cancer cells led to a reduction in F-actin at cell junctions relative to the levels observed in cells expressing APC-WT. Accordingly, APC-m4 cells presented cell junctions with reduced levels of adhesive components as well as perturbed dynamics, including a failure to maintain cell junction length and angle, an increase in the incidence of vertex disruption and a perturbed correlation of velocities between the two vertexes in a junction which shifted from symmetric to asymmetric vertex contraction. In support of the precedents outlined above, our data suggest that the pool of actin nucleated by APC might act as a fence that confines adhesive components within cell junctions and, at the same time, confer force to enable cell junction rearrangements while preserving their integrity and strength.

We also showed that APC-m4 cells were larger and moved more erratically and slowly than APC-WT cells. The larger size of mutant cells might stem from the reduction in E-cadherin, prompting the translocation to the nucleus of the YAP transcription factor⁵⁹. Alternatively, it could be due to the reduction in actin polymerization that in turn affects cell stiffness, area and volume⁵⁶. These observations suggest that APC-driven

actin nucleation activity in colorectal cancer cells may be required for proper shape and cell-cell attachments during cell migration to sustain their directionality and speed.

Conclusion

We propose that actin nucleated by APC acts as a 'force buffer' to support the build-up of adhesive molecules allowing cells to undergo the required rearrangements underlying correct cell junction dynamics. As a result, this actin pool might contribute to sustaining the structure of the epithelial monolayer lining the gut and facilitate its deformation to ultimately render the typical crypts-villi landscape. Then, APC-driven actin nucleation might be involved in the 'epithelial morphology' pathway to control gut organization, independently of the microtubule dynamics and Wnt signaling pathways²². In addition, the effects of APC-driven actin nucleation on directed cell migration in wounded monolayers, suggest that APC alone, or perhaps in coordination with Arp2/3 and/or formins, might be critical in orchestrating directed cell motility along the crypt-villus axis.

Our results provide a further connection between the well-established relevance of actin polymerization activity for the integrity of the gut barrier and the architecture of the gut monolayer on one hand, and APC's standing as the master regulator of gut homeostasis on the other. In our view, APC-mediated actin nucleation activity at cell junctions would support the integrity of the epithelial barrier which is critical to avert infection or inflammatory disorders such as inflammatory bowel disease but also to withstand epithelial cell deformation that could otherwise drive the path to polyps and ultimately to colorectal cancer. Thus, our findings offer a new perspective to explore the relevance of APC-driven cytoskeletal functions in gut morphogenesis and human disease.

Limitations of the study

The major limitation of this study is that as model system, we have used cell monolayers. In such as set ups, cells are not in their physiological environment and interactions with extracellular matrix that can influence the results can be missed. Supporting assays and analysis in intestinal organoids – which mimic patient response in a more physiological context - would validate the effects of APC-driven actin nucleation in collective cell dynamics. However, work on organoids, and especially live imaging studies to monitor cell remodeling and migration is very challenging.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Conceptualization, M.A.J., A.I., L.B.; Methodology & Investigation: M.A.J., A.I., L.B.; Formal Analysis, M.A.J., A.I., L.B., H.M.B., Z.A.B.; Writing: M.A.J., A.I., L.B.; Resources: M.A.J.; Supervision: M.A.J.; Funding Acquisition, M.A.J.

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DECLARATION OF INTERESTS

The authors declare no competing financial interests.

FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1. APC-m4 decreases the levels of F-actin and key molecular components at cell junctions and perturbs cell junction dynamics. See also Figure S1. All data are from SW480 stably expressing APC-WT or APC-m4, except data in E-K panels that are from those stable cells lines additionally transfected with E-cadherin-GFP. **(A)** Qualitative graph showing the percentage of cells that belong to the “normal”, “discontinuous”, and “round” category assigned in function of the appearance of the F-actin label at the cell junctions (see methods). Two-way ANOVA Sidak’s multiple comparisons test was performed to find the statistical differences. ‘****’ is $p < 0.0001$, ‘***’ is $p < 0.001$, and ‘ns’ is not significant. $n(\text{APC-WT}) = 137$, $n(\text{APC-m4}) = 95$. Data are from three independent repeats. **(B)** Representative immunofluorescence images of F-Actin and Occludin. Scale bar = 20 μm . **(C)** Violin plot showing the average F-actin intensity at the cell junctions. The solid line is median and dotted lines are

quartiles. Mann-Whitney U test was performed to find the statistical differences. '****' is $p < 0.0001$. $n(\text{APC-WT}) = 107$, $n(\text{APC-m4}) = 241$. **(D)** Violin plot showing the average Occludin intensity at the cell junctions. The solid line is median and dotted lines are quartiles. Mann-Whitney U test was performed to find the statistical differences. '****' is $p < 0.0001$. $n(\text{APC-WT}) = 107$, $n(\text{APC-m4}) = 195$. **(E)** Representative timelapse images showing E-cadherin-GFP at cell junctions. Scale bar = 5 μm . The color gradient shows the varying signal intensity. White arrows show disrupted cell junction vertexes. **(F)** Graph showing the percentage of cell junctions with junction angles between 0° and 20° . Cell junction angle at time 0 = 0° . Cells: $n = 9$ per condition; Junctions: $n = 9$ per condition for the 11 planes of the timelapse, being that $n=99$ per condition. **(G)** Violin plot showing fold change in cell junction length during the 20 minutes observation window, taking as a reference the time 0 minutes. Cells: $n = 9$ per condition. **(H)** Representative kymographs of cell junctions and violin plot showing cell junction velocity. Junctions: $n(\text{APC-WT}) = 43$, $n(\text{APC-m4}) = 53$. **(I)** Representative kymographs of vertexes of cell junctions and violin plot showing vertex velocity. Vertexes: $n(\text{APC-WT}) = 88$, $n(\text{APC-m4}) = 104$. **(J)** Violin plot showing the difference between the velocity of two vertexes at the same cell junction. Junctions: $n(\text{APC-WT}) = 44$, $n(\text{APC-m4}) = 52$. **(K)** Violin plot showing cells with no (0), one (1) or both (2) junction vertexes disrupted. Cells $n(\text{APC-WT}) = 46$, $n(\text{APC-m4}) = 45$; vertexes per condition for the 11 planes of the timelapse coming from those cells: $n(\text{APC-WT}) = 506$, $n(\text{APC-m4}) = 495$. In panels (G-K), the solid line is median and dotted lines are quartiles. Mann-Whitney U test was performed to find the statistical differences. '****' is $p < 0.0001$. Data in panel (F-K) are from three independent repeats. **(L)** Representative Scanning Electron Microscopy images of the cell junctions. Scale bar = 1 μm , inset = 0.5 μm .

Figure 2. Expression of APC-m4 mutant results in enlarged cells. **(A)** Representative segmentation images from CellPose of HCT116 cells stably expressing APC-WT and APC-m4. **(B)** Violin plot showing the size of individual HCT116 cells shown in (A). $n(\text{APC-WT}) = 1487$, $n(\text{APC-m4}) = 1586$. **(C)** Representative segmentation images from CellPose of SW480 cells stably expressing APC-WT and APC-m4. **(D)** Violin plot showing the size of individual cells SW480 shown in (C). $n(\text{APC-WT}) = 157$, $n(\text{APC-m4}) = 98$. For panels (B) and (D), Mann-Whitney U test was performed to find the statistical difference. '****' is $p < 0.0001$. **(E)** Violin plots showing the size of individual SW480 cells forming monolayers treated with DMSO or SMIFH2. One-way ANOVA Sidak's test was performed to find statistical differences. '****' is $p < 0.0001$, and 'ns' is not significant. $n(\text{APC-WT DMSO}) = 208$, $n(\text{APC-m4 DMSO}) = 165$, $n(\text{APC-WT SMIFH2}) = 187$, and $n(\text{APC-m4 SMIFH2}) = 147$. **(F)** Representative graphs showing FACS data of HCT116 APC-WT and APC-m4 stably expressing cells. **(G)** From the left to the right: Violin plots showing the percentage of HCT116 APC-WT and APC-m4 cells in G1, S, and G2. The solid line is median and dotted lines are quartiles. Mann-Whitney U test was performed to find the statistical difference. 'ns' is not significant, and symbols are three independent repeats.

Figure 3. Expression of APC-m4 mutant causes defects in directionality and speed of colorectal cancer wounded monolayers. See also Figure S2. All data

are from HCT116 cells stably expressing APC-WT or APC-m4. **(A)** Representative wound healing assays showing cells at 0 and 24 hours after scratch. The arrow indicates the direction of the migration front. Scale bar: 100 μm . **(B)** Representative traces of the migration paths of individual cells, moving into a wound site, displayed in horizontal arrays. Black arrow indicates the direction of the migrating cells. **(C-F)** Violin plot showing the directionality (C), velocity (D), Euclidean Distance (E), and Accumulated Distance (F) of individual cells from the edge of the wound during a 24-hour observation window. The red line is the median and the black lines are the quartiles. Mann-Whitney U test was performed to find statistical differences. '****' is $p < 0.0001$. Data in all panels are from three independent repeats. In panels B to F, $n(\text{APC-WT}) = 37$, $n(\text{APC-m4}) = 39$.

Video 1. Related to Figure 1. Representative timelapse showing dynamics of cell junction labeled with E-cadherin GFP in SW480 cells stably expressing APC-WT or APC-m4. Cells were imaged every 2 minutes for 20 min. Video playback is 4 frames per second. Scale bar = 5 μm .

Video 2. Related to Figure 3. Representative timelapse showing the motility of HCT116 stably expressing APC-WT or APC-m4 cells in a wound healing assay. Cells were grown to a monolayer, then wounded, and time lapsed for 24 hours. Images were acquired every 30 minutes. Video playback is 12 frames per second. Scale bar = 100 μm .

STAR METHODS

Detailed methods are provided in the online version of this paper and include the following:

- Key Resources Table
- Resource Availability
 - Lead Contact
 - Materials Availability
 - Data and Code Availability
- Experimental model and subject details
- Method details
- Imaging data analysis
- Statistical analysis

STAR METHODS

RESOURCE AVAILABILITY

Lead Contact

Requests for further information and reagents should be directed to and will be fulfilled by the Lead Contact, M. Angeles Juanes (majuanes@cipf.es).

Materials Availability

This study has generated new cell lines which would be made available upon request to the Lead Contact M. Angeles Juanes.

Data and Code Availability

Data reported in this paper, including codes here generated, have been deposited in Zenodo (zenodo.org) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7114598>, and are available upon request to the lead contact, M. Angeles Juanes.

Experimental Model and Subject Details, including plasmid transfection

HCT116 (#91091005 from Merck, RRID:CVCL_0291) and SW480 (#87092801 from Merck, RRID:CVCL_0546) human colorectal cancer cell lines were grown in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium (DMEM high glucose with pyruvate and L-Glutamine (#41966029; ThermoFisher) supplemented with 10% Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS; # F9423; Sigma-Aldrich) and antibiotics (Penicillin and Streptomycin (#15140-122; ThermoFisher) at 37°C, 95% humidity, and 5% CO₂.

Plasmid transfection was performed using Lipofectamine 3000 (#L3000-015; ThermoFisher) according to the manufacturer's instructions. In addition to the standard protocol, after 4 hours, the transfection medium was removed and fresh pre-warmed DMEM was added to each well.

HCT116 and SW480 colorectal cancer cell lines stably expressing APC-WT and APC-m4 were generated by transfecting each parental cell line with plasmids encoding APC-WT (#16507; Addgene) or APC-m4²³. A plasmid encoding GFP-alone (#54759, Addgene) was used as transfection control. After plasmid transfection, cells were grown in medium containing 600 mg/ml G418 (#10131035; ThermoFisher) until single colonies were observed. Four colonies per condition were picked, APC expression was studied using immunofluorescence assays, and cells were maintained in medium containing 200 mg/ml G418). Clones with comparable APC levels were used in subsequent experiments and for a maximum of 10 passages.

METHOD DETAILS

Immunostaining studies and drug treatments

To determine the APC protein levels in HCT116 and SW480 colorectal cancer cell lines stably expressing APC-WT and APC-m4, cells were seeded on 18 mm² round

coverslips (#631-0153; VWR International Ltd UK). To determine Occludin and F-actin protein levels at cell junctions, cells were seeded on 8-well chambers with collagen IV (#8082, ibidi, Germany) until confluency. To determine cell size from cell monolayers, cells were grown on round coverslips until confluency, then treated with DMSO (as control, #276855, Sigma-Aldrich) or SMIFH2 (20 μ M, #S4826, Sigma-Aldrich) for one hour before proceeding for staining. All cells were fixed with warm 4% paraformaldehyde (#28908, Thermo Scientific) in Phosphate-Buffered Saline (PBS: 2.7 mM KCl, 1.8 mM KH_2PO_4 , 10 mM Na_2HPO_4 , 140 mM NaCl, pH 7.4) (#P4417 Sigma-Aldrich) for 15 minutes, washed once with PBS, permeabilized with 0.1% Triton X-100 (catalogue#; T8787-100ML, Sigma-Aldrich) for 10 minutes, washed once with 1x PBST (1x PBS, 0.1% v/v Tween-20 : catalogue# P1379-100ML; Sigma-Aldrich), blocked with 3% BSA (#A3059-10G; Sigma-Aldrich) for 1 hour at room temperature and incubated overnight at 4°C with anti-APC C-terminus (1:250, Abcam, ab154906, RRID:AB_2861396), anti-Occludin (1:300, Abcam, RRID:AB_1661439), accordingly. Coverslips were then washed with 1x PBST three times for 5 minutes each and incubated with secondary antibodies Alexa-488 anti-rabbit goat (1:1000; A32723, RRID:AB_2633275, Thermo Fisher Scientific) or Alexa-568 anti-rabbit (1:1000, # A-11011, Invitrogen-Thermo Fisher Scientific), along with Alexa-568 Phalloidin (1:1000; #A12380, Invitrogen-Thermo Fisher Scientific) or Alexa-488 Phalloidin (1:1000; A12379, Invitrogen-Thermo Fisher Scientific) to stain F-actin, for 1 hour at room temperature. Next, coverslips were washed with 1x PBST twice for 5 minutes each and mounted on glass slides (#N/A141, ACADEMY) using Aquamount mounting medium (#14-390-5, Thermo Fisher Scientific).

Cells were imaged on a Leica DMI8 microscope with a 20x objective (HC PL FLUOTAR 20x/0.75) equipped with a Leica DFC9000GT camera, or in a Leica TCS SP8 SMD laser scanning microscope equipped with a EL6000 FI light source, FOV scanner SP8, - 3.6 kHz tuneable speed, 60x water objective (HC PL APO CS2 20x/0.75). SP8 images were captured as stacks (11 planes, 0.5 μ m steps) in conventional confocal or lightning mode which is based on adaptive image reconstruction⁶⁰ at 1-10% laser power using photomultiplier tube (PTM) detectors in sequential mode at 488 and 568 nm, and Pinhole: 1.00 AU, in a LAS X Life Science Microscope Software (version 3.5.5.19976, RRID:SCR_013673).

Live-cell imaging

To investigate cell-cell junction dynamics, SW480 cells stably expressing APC-WT and APC-m4 were seeded in ibidi 35 mm² dishes pre-coated with collagen I (50201; ibidi, Germany). Once confluent, cells were co-transfected with plasmids encoding E-cadherin-GFP – adherent junction marker (#280009, Addgene), and Life-Actin-mCherry (as control, #54491, Addgene). 24 hours post-transfection, medium was changed to L15 (Leibovitz, Cat# 21083027, ThermoFisher) and cells were imaged live every 2 minutes for 20 minutes using a Leica SP8 SMD confocal laser scanning microscope equipped with a EL6000 FI light source 60x water objective (HC PL APO

CS2 20x/0.75), connected to H301-EC-LG-BL holder and Okolab stage top incubator H301-T-UNIT-BL-PLUS, Okolab CO2-UNIT-BL and HM-ACTIVE Humidity Controllers to maintain cells at 37°C with 5% CO₂ and 95% humidity. Images were captured as stacks (3 z-stacks with a 0.6 μm step) using photomultiplier tube (PTM) detectors in sequential mode at 488 and 568 nm, and Pinhole: 1.00 AU, in a LAS X Life Science Microscope Software (version 3.5.5.19976).

For wound healing assays, 80,000 cells - HCT116 or SW480 APC-WT or APC-m4 - were seeded on 8-well chambers with collagen IV (Ibidi, Germany) containing DMEM medium containing high glucose buffer (Gibco, Life Technologies), 10% FBS, 20 mM L-glutamine, 1 mM sodium pyruvate, and 5 ml of Penicillin-Streptomycin antibiotics and incubated at 37°C, 5% CO₂, and 95% humidity. Once cells were confluent, the medium was removed and replaced with fresh medium but without FBS for 6 - 7 hours. After that time, axial wounds were performed using a standard pipette tip. Then, serum-free medium was removed, and cells were washed twice with PBS (#20012027, ThermoFisher). Next, the chambers were replenished with DMEM medium containing 10% FBS. To monitor wound closure, SW480 and HCT116 cells were imaged at 30 min intervals for 24 hr or 48 hr, respectively, maintaining cells at 37°C with 5% CO₂ and 95% humidity using an Okolab stage top incubator H301-T-UNIT-BL-PLUS, Okolab CO2-UNIT-BL and HM-ACTIVE Humidity Controllers connected to a H301-K-FRAME holder adapted and an inverted Leica DMi8 microscope (Leica microsystems). Images were captured using an HC PL FLUOTAR 10x/0.30 air objective, and a Leica DFC9000GT camera using a LAS X Life Science Microscope Software (version 3.5.5.19976).

Imaging data analysis

For imaging data analysis, ImageJ/Fiji (v1.53k, RRID:SCR_003070/v2.3, RRID:SCR_002285), python (v2.12, RRID:SCR_008394), Microsoft Excel (v16, RRID:SCR_016137), GraphPad Prism (v9, RRID:SCR_002798) and Adobe Illustrator (v26.5, RRID:SCR_010279) were used.

Fluorescence intensity measurements

To measure APC protein levels in cells, a custom macro in Fiji was used to generate and save sum slices z-projections for all images. Next, cell boundaries were manually drawn on these images and saved in a separate folder. Another custom macro in Fiji was then used to measure integrated density, mean grey value, and cell area. Finally, corrected total cell fluorescence (CTCF) was calculated using the following formula:

CTCF = Integrated density – (Area of selected cell X Mean fluorescence of background readings)

To measure F-Actin and Occludin protein levels at the cell junctions, immunofluorescence images were opened in Fiji and cell boundaries were manually traced from the F-Actin channel. Regions of interest (ROIs) from F-Actin channel were saved and over imposed with cells/junctions in the Occludin channel. Mean grey values were obtained in ImageJ for both channels and saved as .CSV. Data was then analysed and plotted in GraphPad Prism.

Qualitative assessment of the appearance of cell junctions

To qualitatively assess the effect on cell-cell junctions of APC-driven actin nucleation impairment, a criterion based on both the healthiness and morphology of the cell junction of each cell was established. We divided cells in three different categories: '*normal*', '*discontinuous*', and '*round*'. *Normal* cells were defined as cells with all, or at least three cell junctions labelled with F-actin throughout the cell junction (i.e. continuous signal), whereas *discontinuous* cells were those cells with two or more disrupted cell junctions, therefore not all cell junctions were properly labeled. '*Round*' cells were defined as cells that have lost their typical

morphology and acquired roughly a circular shape. Mitotic cells were excluded from the measurements. Qualitative count was performed in a blind way by several members of the team for three different sets of images. The percentage of cells corresponding to each category was calculated using Microsoft Excel, and then plotted with GraphPad Prism (version 9.0; GraphPad Software, La Jolla, CA).

Cell size quantification

For cell size quantification of individual cells in monolayers, we first generated TIFF files of the middle frame of F-actin immunofluorescence images using Fiji. Then, individual cell size was quantified using a deep-learning-based segmentation method called CellPose⁽³⁷⁾, RRID:SCR_021716). Briefly, parameters to segment cells were chosen in function of the cell diameter, which we estimated using Fiji. Images were loaded into CellPose and "CP" was selected as model to segment cells. The outlines of the cells were saved as .txt. Original TIFF files were opened in Fiji, the macro called imagej_roi_converter.py was run and outlines were over imposed on the monolayer image. For accurateness of the results, cells from the edges of the images were manually scrutinized and removed from the counts. We measured cell areas which were saved as .CSV. Data was then analysed and plotted with GraphPad Prism (version 9.0; GraphPad Software, La Jolla, CA).

Cell migration analysis

Individual cells migrating at the edge of the wound were tracked using the manual tracking from ImageJ, whose coordinates were saved as a .txt file. Those files were then exported into Chemotaxis and Migration Tool version 2.0 software (Ibidi, Germany RRID: SCR_022708) to obtain migratory related parameters such as the

directionality, speed [$\mu\text{m}/\text{min}$], Euclidean Distance [μm], and Accumulated Distance [μm] of each cell tracked Data were combined from time-lapse image series collected from at least three independent experimental days, then plotted with GraphPad Prism (version 9.0; GraphPad Software, La Jolla, CA).

Cell junction analysis

To measure cell junction length, a line was manually drawn on the cell junction using the “segmented line” tool in Fiji and line length was measured using the “measure” tool. To calculate the junction angle, a straight line was drawn joining the two vertexes and the line angle was measured using the “measure” tool. The minimum angle was termed angle 0 and the rest were normalised by subtracting the minimum angle. Junction vertex disruption was qualitatively analysed. Junctions with none, one or both vertexes disrupted were labelled as 0, 1 and 2 vertexes disrupted, respectively.

To measure junction velocities, kymographs were generated by drawing a straight line perpendicular to the junction using the “multi-kymograph” tool in Fiji. Next, the “segmented line” tool was used to trace the junction by connecting maximum pixel intensity in each time frame. To measure vertex velocities: kymographs were generated by drawing a straight line along the junction joining the two vertexes using the “multi-kymograph” tool in Fiji. Next, the “segmented line” tool was used to trace each vertex by connecting the maximum pixel intensity on each side of the junction in each time frame. Finally, velocities were calculated by measuring the length of the segmented line using the “measure” tool and dividing it by time.

All data was plotted in GraphPad Prism.

Scanning Electron Microscopy

To study the ultrastructure of the cell junctions, 200000 HCT116 cells were seeded on collagen-precoated (Advanced BioMatrix - PureCol® Solution, 3 mg/ml (bovine) #5005, AdvanceBiomatrix) 18 mm² round coverslips. After cells grew to confluency (approximately 24 hours), cells were fixed with 2.5% glutaraldehyde (Polyscience, Cat# 01909-10) in 0.1M Sodium Phosphate buffer pH 7.2 for 3 hours. Samples were then washed three times with 0.1mM Sodium Phosphate buffer pH 7.2 for 10 minutes. Next, samples were post-fixed in 2% Osmium tetroxide (OsO₄, # O5500-250MG, Sigma-Aldrich) in buffer and left on ice for one hour. A second round of three 10-minutes wash in 0.1mM Sodium Phosphate buffer pH 7.2 was performed. After that, samples were fully dehydrated in a graded series of ethanol solutions (10 minutes per solution), followed by hexamethyldisilazane (HMDS, Merck Life Science Ltd, Cat# 804324) twice for 10 minutes. Samples were left at room temperature overnight to ensure full evaporation of HMDS. Finally, samples were mounted and sputtered coat with gold and Palladium using a SC7640 sputter coater, before observation using a Jeol 6490 scanning electron microscope operating at 5kV.

Statistical analysis

All experiments were repeated multiple times, as indicated in figure legends. Data were pooled and, if required, analysed further in Microsoft Excel (v16), and plotted in GraphPad Prism (v9.0; GraphPad Software, La Jolla, CA). Figure legends specify the n, errors, and the statistical test used. Data distributions were tested for normality using the D'Agostino-Pearson omnibus normality test, and statistical differences among conditions were calculated using ordinary one-way or two-way ANOVA Holm-Sidak or Tukey multiple comparisons tests, Mann-Whitney U test (non-parametric) or unpaired t-test with Welch's correction (parametric) in GraphPad Prism (v9.0; GraphPad Software, La Jolla, CA). Differences were considered significant if p-value was <0.05 (*), <0.01(**), <0.001(***), or < 0.0001 (****), as indicated in each figure legend.

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Figure S1. Related to Figure 1. Generation of stable colorectal cancer cell lines and cell junction integrity effects in APC-m4 mutant cells. (A) Experiment regimen. **(B)** Representative immunofluorescence images of HCT116 colorectal cancer (parental, and stably expressing stably either APC-WT or APC-m4) cells treated as in (A) showing APC and F-actin protein signals. Scale bar = 15 μ m, inset = 5 μ m. **(C)** Violin plot showing APC signal in HCT116 colorectal cancer (parental, and stably expressing either APC-WT or APC-m4) cells, and from the corresponding clones (C01-04). n(parental) = 37, n(APC-WT:C01) = 29, n(APC-WT:C02) = 33, n(APC-WT:C03) = 31, n(APC-WT:C04) = 35, n(APC-m4:C01) = 32, n(APC-m4:C02) = 30, n(APC-m4:C03) = 35 and n(APC-m4:C04) = 25. **(D)** Violin plot showing APC signal of SW480 APC-WT and APC-m4 stably expressing cells, and from the corresponding clones (C01-04). n(APC-WT:C01) = 83, n(APC-WT:C02) = 94, n(APC-WT:C03) = 86, n(APC-WT:C04) = 95, n(APC-m4:C01) = 94, n(APC-m4:C02) = 87, n(APC-m4:C03) = 96 and n(APC-m4:C04) = 92. Data in panels (C-D) are from two independent repeats. The solid line is median and dotted lines are quartiles. One-way ANOVA with Tukey correction was performed to find the statistical differences. ‘*’ is $p < 0.5$, ‘***’ is $p < 0.01$, ‘****’ is $p < 0.001$ and ‘*****’ is $p < 0.0001$. **(E)** Qualitative graph showing the percentage of HCT116 APC-WT or APC-m4 cells that belongs to the “normal”, “discontinuous”, and “round” category. Two-way ANOVA Sidak’s multiple comparisons test was performed. ‘*****’ is $p < 0.0001$,

and 'ns' is not significant. $n(\text{APC-WT}) = 507$, $n(\text{APC-m4}) = 632$. Data were obtained from three independent repeats.

Figure S2. Related to Figure 3. Expression of APC-m4 mutant causes defects in directionality and speed of colorectal cancer wounded monolayers. All data are from SW480 cells stably expressing APC-WT or APC-m4. **(A)** Representative wound healing assays showing cells at 0 and 23 hours after scratch. The arrow indicates the direction of the migration front. Scale bar: 100 μm . **(B)** Representative traces of the migration paths of individual cells, moving into a wound site, displayed in horizontal arrays. Black arrow indicates the direction of the migrating cells. **(C-E)** Violin plot showing the directionality (B), velocity (C), Euclidean distance (D), and accumulated distance (E) of individual cells from the edge of the wound during a 23-hour observation window. The red line is the median and the black lines are the quartiles. Mann-Whitney U-test was performed to find the statistical differences. '*' is $p < 0.05$ and '****' is $p < 0.0001$. Data in panels C to F are from three independent repeats. In panels B to F, $n(\text{APC-WT}) = 20$, $n(\text{APC-m4}) = 10$.